

Form-process feedbacks in loess landform development; gully erosion the Chinese Loess Plateau

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Abstract—Gully development is a common phenomenon in the Loess Plateau of China, causing profound impacts on regional soil erosion and ecological environment. Exploring the development rate and trend of regional loess gullies can provide a reference for regional soil and water conservation work. In this study, taking the Beiluo River Basin on the Loess Plateau as the study area, we proposed an object-oriented classification method using topographic skeleton lines to decipher the 2009 and 2021 images of the study area, from which the gully development rate and the amount of material loss were calculated. The results show that the proposed image classification method can effectively decipher the gully boundaries, and the overall classification accuracy can reach 88.7%. In the past 12 years, the total area of gully expansion was 55 km², and the average annual expansion rate was 4.58 km²/year. Gully erosion is generally in a more active state, dominated by gully head erosion and sidewall erosion. Sediment migration is mainly concentrated in the loess gullies with the highest erosion intensity. Sediment migration is also concentrated in the lower part of the basin, especially in low elevation areas such as loess gullies, showing sensitivity to topographic differences. The results of correlation analysis showed that the gully development stage was positively correlated with the erosion volume, and there was no obvious correlation with the erosion area and the proportion of loess landform types.

I. INTRODUCTION

Loess gully erosion is one of the most severe and common environmental hazards in the loess landforms [1]. Severe soil loss and soil degradation caused by gully erosion are considered the leading cause of sedimentation production [2]. In the development process of loess landform, different erosion intensities and time scales have formed loess gully systems with a coherent structure, including spoon gully, shallow gully, bank gully, and valley gully

[3]. These gully systems have different scales and levels, and they also represent the erosion development history of loess landforms and are essential research objects for direct analysis of the development of loess landforms. Monitoring the development of loess gullies and the spatial distribution of sediment transport is significant for explaining the differences in loess landforms and the evolution of the entire Chinese Loess Plateau (CLP). Due to the importance of gully erosion research, increasing attention has been paid to the field recently [4-6]. Among them, the monitoring of the gully's erosion rate is an important branch. The erosion of gullies is influenced by many factors (such as terrain, rainfall, vegetation coverage, etc.), and the development rate is not stable, which increases the requirements for data accuracy and measurement methods. In the loess gully monitoring method, several different technologies are involved, such as unmanned aerial vehicle [7] photogrammetry, 3D laser scanning, global positioning system, and remote sensing image interpretation. UAV photogrammetry and 3D laser scanning are considered to be effective methods to obtain high-precision gully monitoring data and has been successfully implemented in many studies [8-11]. However, these methods are mostly applied on small areas and are challenging to apply on large spatial areas [7,12]. Moreover, GPS technology is another popular approach to acquire multi-temporal terrain data. However, this approach still needs numerous sampling points obtained manually to spatial interpolation and thus is not suitable for large area [8,13]. Relatively few studies have been reported on loess gully erosion using these three methods at larger spatial areas. In recent years, with the development of remote sensing satellite technology, the spatial and temporal resolution of acquired remote sensing images have been significantly improved, making satellite images have irreplaceable

potential in monitoring large-area gully erosion [14-15]. The extent of gullies can be accurately extracted on the basis of high-resolution remote sensing images combined with auxiliary data such as DEMs and vector rivers data, which also makes it possible to monitor gully dynamics on a large area. Thus, the remote sensing interpretation method based on high-resolution satellite images can be an appropriate alternative way to detect the boundary changes of loess gully [16-17].

Summarizing previous studies, many methods and theories have been proposed to analyze the development and evolution of loess landforms, including geological dating [18], feature expression method [19], space for time theory [20], subbasin monitoring simulation method [12]. Some studies have also noticed and explored the differences of loess landforms [21-22]. These works have contributed to the broader understanding of the formation mechanism and evolution of loess landforms. However, the current theories on loess landform evolution are mainly based on a macroscopic and holistic perspective of the entire CLP, and the expressions of the differences in loess landforms are primarily concentrated in a certain loess type (for example, loess plateau) and lack spatial distribution characteristics. A more specific perspective is needed to analyze the evolution and internal differences of the loess landform. To this end, a typical basin in the CLP was selected to classify the loess landform types based on the commonly used object-oriented image analysis (OBIA) method.

The Beiluo River basin is one of the important basins in the CLP. This basin is in the hinterland of the Loess Plateau and has typical loess landform features. Surface erosion and soil loss are severe in the basin, which is one of the important sediment export sources of the Yellow River. Typical loess landform types such as loess table, loess ridge, and loess hill are distributed. Due to the differences and hierarchical distribution of landform types in this watershed, it is an ideal sample area for studying the erosion process and spatial differences of loess landforms. The specific objectives of this study were to: (1) use the object-oriented method to classify the loess landform types in the study area, (2) quantitatively analyze the morphological and spatial distribution differences of loess landform types based on the adopted indicators, (3) estimate the gully changes using two periods of loess gully data, which are obtained by interpreting two high-resolution images with a 12-year interval.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Study area

The Lower Beiluo River Basin is located at the hinterland of the CLP (107°32' ~110°06' E, 34°54' ~37°19' N). The overall elevation is high in the northwest and low in the southeast (Fig. 1). The basin has a continental monsoon climate, with an average annual rainfall between 510 and 540 mm concentrated in July to September. Intense rainfall leads to soil loss in this basin

and affects about 64% of the total area of the watershed [12]. The study area has typical loess landform features, and the loess landform patterns of the basin have significant regional differences in spatial distribution. The main landform types of the basin from top to bottom are the hilly-gullied loess region in the upper reaches, the plateau gully region in the middle reaches, and the plain terrace region in the lower reaches. Among them, after the transition from the plateau gully in the middle reaches, the lower reaches' topography gradually becomes flat. According to the landform type map of the CLP, the landform types in the study area include loess plateau tableland, residual tableland and gully, and low bedrock hill.

Figure 1. Location of study area and distribution of selected sample areas

B. Data Sources

The data used in the research are topographical, hydrological, and image-based. The topographical data were derived from the NASA SRTM DEM released by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) in 2020 with a spatial resolution of 30 m. and is considered the highest-quality freely-available product with global coverage [23]. The DEM data themselves were not enough to meet the requirements of accurate classification for the gully scale used here. High-resolution remote sensing images were used to produce higher density spectral and texture information. 5 m resolution imagery downloaded from Planet Explorer (<https://www.planet.com/explorer/>) was used. The image data contain two periods of 2009 and 2021.

III. METHODS

(1) Loess landform interpretation based on the object-oriented method

The object-oriented method was adopted in the study to interpret the loess landform types of the study area. The two most important steps in the classification process are the segmentation of multiple layers and selecting classification features. MRS is a bottom-up region merging technology starting from a pixel object. The image object generated after the segmentation process is the smallest unit for further image interpretation. Classification feature selection needs as much information as possible to distinguish the segmented objects, so multiple input layers are necessary. For this purpose, DEM data, derived terrain factor layers (slope, terrain relief and curvature), remote sensing images, and vector river data are used in classification experiments.

(2) Two-dimensional application of the morphological method: Hydrological routing

To determine the spatial patterns of sediment transport rate in loess gullies, a two-dimensional application of the morphological method was employed. This method was first proposed by Lane et al. [24]. In previous studies, this method has been proven to be feasible for sedimentation transport in experimental gully systems. In regions dominated by topography, the sediment transport path can be regarded as a classic multi-flow hydrological routing problem. The rate of transport is determined by their slope changes. Accordingly, the transport rate R_k of sediments in any direction k can be defined as:

$$R_k = \left(\frac{\tan s_k}{\sum_1^8 \tan s_k} \right)^\alpha \times [Q_s + \rho(1 - \rho)\Delta V_{ij}] \quad (1)$$

Where s_k is the gradient of the surrounding cells k ; Q_s is the sediment volume received by cell k from the surrounding cells; $\rho(1-\rho)$ is equal to the bulk density, and α is the parameter that controls the degree of flow diffusion.

IV. RESULTS

(1) Loess gully erosion status

The loess tableland is a relatively complete and flat surface remaining during the erosion process of the CLP. Therefore, we assume that the elevation value of the loess tableland represents the elevation of the original terrain, ignoring the weak erosion and accumulation of the loess tableland during the evolution of the CLP. The original terrain of the study area is simulated by extracting the elevation points on the loess tablelands in and around the study area and then performing spatial interpolation. To estimate the volume and quality of surface erosion, elevation changes between the two periods of DEMs were computed by subtracting the values in the earlier DEMs from those in the later DEMs. It can be roughly calculated that the volume of the material eroded by the surface is $1.01 \times 10^{11} \text{ m}^3$ and the weight of the material eroded is about $1.40 \times 10^{14} \text{ kg}$ (the average loess soil density is 1.39 g/cm^3).

Figure 2. Two-dimensional sediment transport volume estimates (note that the negative transport volume is set to zero for visualization)

The monitoring results show that the gully area detected was 1663 km^2 in 2009, accounting for 46.5% of the total study area (Fig. 4a). The spatial distribution of loess gullies shows a clear "tree-view" structure from south to north. According to the standard for classification and gradation of soil erosion (SL190-2007) issued by the Ministry of Water Resources of China, the soil erosion intensity of the whole area is classified as extremely strong. By 2021, the area of the loess gullies has increased to $1,718 \text{ km}^2$, with an area increased by 55 km^2 in 12 years and an average increase rate of $4.58 \text{ km}^2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Fig. 4b).

Figure 3. Detected loess gully boundaries in 2009 and 2021

V. CONCLUSION

In this article, we provide a reference for describing the morphology of the loess landform and monitoring large-area loess gully changes, which can help to understand the development and evolution of the loess landform in-depth. However, we realized that the loess gully erosion results of the two-dimensional morphological method are preliminary and rough due to lacking critical parameters (e.g. gully depth and volume). Higher-precision gully monitoring data and multi-scale resolution data are still needed in further studies to obtain more accurate and applicable results.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Cai Qiangguo. 2001. 'Soil erosion and management on the Loess Plateau', *Journal of Geographical Sciences*, 11: 53-70. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02837376>
- [2] Wang Ranghu, Shuwen Zhang, Luoman Pu, Jiuchun Yang, Chaobin Yang, Jing Chen, Cong Guan, Qing Wang, Dan Chen, Bolin Fu, and Xuejia Sang. 2016. 'Gully Erosion Mapping and Monitoring at Multiple Scales Based on Multi-Source Remote Sensing Data of the Sancha River Catchment, Northeast China', *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi5110200>
- [3] Na Jiaming, Xin Yang, Guoan Tang, Weiqin Dang, and Josef Strobl. 2020. 'Population Characteristics of Loess Gully System in the Loess Plateau of China', *Remote Sensing*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12162639>
- [4] Li Zhen, Yan Zhang, Qingke Zhu, Song Yang, Hongjun Li, and Huan Ma. 2017. 'A gully erosion assessment model for the Chinese Loess Plateau based on changes in gully length and area', *Catena*, 148: 195-203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2016.04.018>
- [5] Cao Jianjun, Guoan Tang, Xuan Fang, Yongjuan Liu, Ying Zhu, Jinlian Li, and Wolfgang Wagner. 2020. 'Identification of Active Gully Erosion Sites in the Loess Plateau of China Using MF-DFA', *Remote Sensing*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12030589>
- [6] Kariminejad Narges, Mauro Rossi, Mohsen Hosseinalizadeh, Hamid Reza Pourghasemi, and M. Santosh. 2020. 'Gully head modelling in Iranian Loess Plateau under different scenarios', *Catena*, 194: 104769. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2020.104769>
- [7] Guan Yabing, Shengtian Yang, Changsen Zhao, Hezhen Lou, Ke Chen, Chunbin Zhang, and Bowei Wu. 2021. 'Monitoring long-term gully erosion and topographic thresholds in the marginal zone of the Chinese Loess Plateau', *Soil and Tillage Research*, 205: 104800. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2020.104800>
- [8] Wu Yongqiu, QiuHong Zheng, Yongguang Zhang, Baoyuan Liu, Hong Cheng, and Yanzai Wang. 2008. 'Development of gullies and sediment production in the black soil region of northeastern China', *Geomorphology*, 101: 683-91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2008.03.008>
- [9] Daba Shibr, Wolfgang Rieger, and Peter Strauss. 2003. 'Assessment of gully erosion in eastern Ethiopia using photogrammetric techniques', *Catena*, 50: 273-91. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0341-8162\(02\)00135-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0341-8162(02)00135-2)
- [10] Betts Harley D, Noel A. Trustrum, and Ronald C. De Rose. 2003. 'Geomorphic changes in a complex gully system measured from sequential digital elevation models, and implications for management', *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 28: 1043-58. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.500>
- [11] Stöcker Claudia, Anette Eltner, and Pierre Karrasch. 2015. 'Measuring gullies by synergetic application of UAV and close range photogrammetry — A case study from Andalusia, Spain', *Catena*, 132: 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2015.04.004>
- [12] Wu Hongyan, Ximeng Xu, Fenli Zheng, Chao Qin, and Xu He. 2018. 'Gully morphological characteristics in the loess hilly-gully region based on 3D laser scanning technique', *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 43: 1701-10. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.4332>
- [13] Cheng Hong, Xueyong Zou, Yongqiu Wu, Chunlai Zhang, QiuHong Zheng, and Zhangyan Jiang. 2007. 'Morphology parameters of ephemeral gully in characteristics hillslopes on the Loess Plateau of China', *Soil and Tillage Research*, 94: 4-14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2006.06.007>
- [14] Muñoz-Robles Carlos, Nick Reid, Paul Frazier, Matthew Tighe, Sue V. Briggs, and Brian Wilson. 2010. 'Factors related to gully erosion in woody encroachment in south-eastern Australia', *Catena*, 83: 148-57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2010.08.002>
- [15] Desprats J F, D Raclot, M Rousseau, O Cerdan, M Garcin, Y Le Bissonnais, A Ben Slimane, J Fouche, and D Monfort-Climent. 2013. 'Mapping Linear Erosion Features Using High and very High Resolution Satellite Imagery', *Land Degradation & Development*, 24: 22-32. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.1094>
- [16] Zhang Shuwen, Fei Li, Tianqi Li, Jiuchun Yang, Kun Bu, Liping Chang, Wenjuan Wang, and Yechao Yan. 2015. 'Remote sensing monitoring of gullies on a regional scale: A case study of Kebai region in Heilongjiang Province, China', *Chinese Geographical Science*, 25: 602-11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11769-015-0780-z>
- [17] Teasdale Gregg N, and E. Barber Michael. 2008. 'Aerial Assessment of Ephemeral Gully Erosion from Agricultural Regions in the Pacific Northwest', *Journal of Irrigation and Drainage Engineering*, 134: 807-14. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9437\(2008\)134:6\(807\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9437(2008)134:6(807))
- [18] Stevens T, A Carter, T P Watson, P Vermeesch, S Andò, A F Bird, H Lu, E. Garzanti, M. A. Cottam, and I. Sevastjanova. 2013. 'Genetic linkage between the Yellow River, the Mu Us desert and the Chinese Loess Plateau', *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 78: 355-68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2012.11.032>
- [19] Rinaldo Andrea, Ignacio Rodriguez - Iturbe, Riccardo Rigon, Rafael L Bras, Ede Ijjasz - Vasquez, and Alessandro Marani. 1992. 'Minimum energy and fractal structures of drainage networks', *Water resources research*, 28: 2183-95. <https://doi.org/10.1029/92WR00801>
- [20] Huang Xiaoli, Guoan Tang, Tongxin Zhu, Hu Ding, and Jiaming Na. 2019. 'Space-for-time substitution in geomorphology', *Journal of Geographical Sciences*, 29: 1670-80. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11442-019-1684-0>
- [21] Yuan Shuang, Qiang Xu, Kuanyao Zhao, Xuan Wang, and Cuilin Wang. 2020. 'Geomorphological classification and evolution of plateau-beam-loess hills in Heshui county of the east Gansu province', *Geographical Research*, 08: 1920-33. <https://doi.org/10.11821/dlyj020190988>
- [22] Liu Yongjuan, Jianjun Cao, Liping Wang, Xuan Fang, and Wolfgang Wagner. 2020. 'Regional features of topographic relief over the Loess Plateau, China: evidence from ensemble empirical mode decomposition', *Frontiers of Earth Science*, 14: 695-710. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11707-020-0819-z>
- [23] Uuemaa Evelyn, Sander Ahi, Bruno Montibeller, Merle Muru, and Alexander Knoch. 2020. 'Vertical Accuracy of Freely Available Global Digital Elevation Models (ASTER, AW3D30, MERIT, TanDEM-X, SRTM, and NASADEM)', *Remote Sensing*, 12, no. 21: 3482. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12213482>
- [24] Lane S N, K S Richards, and J H Chandler. 1995. 'Morphological Estimation of the Time-Integrated Bed Load Transport Rate', *Water resources research*, 31: 761-72. <https://doi.org/10.1029/94WR01726>